

CHANGING PERSPECTIVE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASS WITH REFERENCE TO MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE

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Teaching, one of the noblest professions in the world, is dedicated to bring about revolution each and every day. Given to moulding a new Einstein, a new Tagore or a new Gandhi with each passing day, a teacher comes across a variety of challenges in the class room; especially an English language teacher. Majority of India lives in remote rural areas where the teaching of English language begins as late as in the late primary school years. By this time a child develops a lifelong phobia against the language which is very difficult to remove in later years. Developing affinity with the language in college becomes a big challenge for the teacher.

As "humanism" started in the later 20th century, the strict, with the cane teacher changed himself into a student friendly guide. The authoritative instructions gave way to the student focused mode of education. In the past, intelligence was a fixed, static entity at birth which was defined operationally as the ability to answer items on IQ tests. Gradually educators started paying attention to the real learning and understanding; learners' affective factors (e.g., their feelings, emotions, tension, anxiety, frustration, needs, interests, motivation, and confidence, etc.) rather than focusing on rote memory. Then we have witnessed the birth and maturing of some innovative ELT approaches, methods, and techniques during the 70s to the 80s, such as The Silent Way, Community Language Learning, Total Physical Response (TPR), Suggestopedia, The Natural Approach, Communicative Approach, cooperative learning, interactive learning, whole language learning, task-based learning. In 1985 Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences, described in *Frames of Mind*, sparked a revolution of sorts in classrooms around the world, a mutiny against the notion that human beings have a single, fixed intelligence. The passion with which educators accepted his theory that we have multiple intelligences surprised Gardner himself. "It obviously spoke to some sense that people had that kids weren't all the same and that the tests we had only skimmed the surface about the differences among kids," Gardner said. His multiple intelligences (MI) theory ignited an era of educational innovation not only in the United States but throughout the world. Teachers started recognizing the variety of the learners in their learning styles, learning potentials, etc. and appreciate the development of learning strategies on the part of the learners.

Another highly prevailing challenge at higher level of education particularly engineering is that the

teaching fraternity is not imbibing the changes needed. Ashutosh Biswal (2007) says, "... we live in a time of rapid change where change itself is changing and becoming faster ... It has been observed that the development of any society depends upon the dynamic nature of its education systems ... teachers can be manipulated to make education system developed." In the recent decades it has been much argued upon that human minds have multiple forms of knowledge. Now the concept of cramming and learning is the thing of the past. It has been proved that different students have different "Learning Styles" or "Multiple intelligence". According to Howard Gardner, Multiple Intelligences are seven different ways to demonstrate intellectual ability. Howard Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences utilizes aspects of cognitive and developmental psychology, anthropology, and sociology to explain the human intellect. Although Gardner had been working towards the concept of Multiple Intelligences for many years prior. As Gardner (1993:12) states: It is of the utmost importance that we recognize and nurture all of the varied of human intelligences, and all of the combination of intelligence. We are all so different largely because we all have different combinations of intelligences. If we recognize this, I think we will have at least a better chance of dealing appropriately with the many problems that we face in the world.

In order to make a clear distinction between intelligence with its biological origin and a talent/skill, Gardner asserts that each intelligence must satisfy all or a majority of the following criteria, namely brain damage studies, exceptional individuals, developmental history, evolutionary history, psychometric findings, psychological tasks, core operations, and symbol system (Christison, 1998). Up to the present, he has proposed a schema of eight intelligences and suggests that there are probably many others that we have not yet been able to test (Gardner, 1995). A summary of Gardner's eight intelligences is given as follows:

1. Verbal/Linguistic Intelligence is the ability to use language effectively and creatively both orally and in writing. This intelligence can be seen in such people as poets, playwrights, storytellers, actors, orators, novelists, public speakers, and comedians.
2. Logical/Mathematical Intelligence is the ability to use numbers effectively, to recognize abstract patterns, to discern relationships and to reason well. The intelligence

can be seen in such people as scientists, computer programmers, accountant, lawyers, bankers, and, of course, mathematicians.

3. **Visual/Spatial Intelligence** involves the ability to sense form, space, color, line, and shape including the ability to graphically represent visual or spatial ideas. This intelligence can be seen in such people as architects, graphic artists, cartographers, industrial design draftspersons, and, of course, visual artists (painters and sculptors).
4. **Bodily/Kinesthetic Intelligence** is the ability to use one's body to express oneself and to solve problems. This intelligence can be seen in such people as actors, athletes, mimes, dancers, and inventors.
5. **Musical/Rhythmic Intelligence** involves the ability to recognize tonal patterns and a sensibility to rhythm, pitch, melody, etc. This intelligence can be seen in advertising professionals (those who write catchy jingles to sell a product), performance musicians, rock musicians, dance bands and music composers.
6. **Interpersonal Intelligence** involves the ability to understand people's moods, feelings, motivations and intentions. It includes the ability to work cooperatively with others in a group and to communicate, verbally and nonverbally, with other people. This form of intelligence is usually highly developed in such people as counselors, teachers, therapists, politicians, and religious leaders.
7. **Intrapersonal Intelligence** involves the ability to understand the internal aspects of the self and to practice self-discipline. This intelligence can be seen in such people as philosophers, psychiatrists, spiritual counselors, and cognitive pattern researchers.
8. **Naturalist Intelligence** involves the ability to recognize and classify plants, minerals, and animals, including rocks, grass, and all variety of flora and fauna. It also includes the ability to recognize cultural artifacts like cars, sneakers, etc. The intelligence can be seen in such people as farmers, hunters, zookeepers, gardeners, cooks, veterinarians, nature guide, and forest rangers.

With the reference of Christison (1996:10-11), we can use the four steps method to show how MI theory applies to ELT. The first step is to identify the activities frequently used in our classes and categorize them to each particular type of intelligence. A good language teacher should be well aware of different strengths of different students. With the understanding of multiple intelligence theory the teacher can cater to the needs of students with different learning styles and learning potentials.

There are four key points that educators find attractive about the MI theory:

1. Each person possesses all eight intelligences.
2. Intelligences can be developed.
3. Intelligences work together in complex ways. No intelligence really exists by itself in life. Intelligences are always interaction with each other.

4. There are many different ways to be intelligent. There is no standard set of attributes that one must have in order to be considered intelligent.

Reception and understanding can be achieved through many different language teaching methods. The silent way emphasizes the student's inner thinking. Total physical response emphasizes language learning through physical action while suggestopedia emphasizes the use of music to enhance understanding and learning. The Communicative approach as well as cooperative learning lays stress upon the importance of interpersonal relationships. For example the teacher wants the students to enhance their vocabulary bank; not all the students would be good at memorizing antonyms, synonyms etc. The teacher can then make use of some game like *Domino Charades* for logical learners, a crossword can be played for mathematical learners, a concert for musical students, a play can be enacted for the visual learners.

Now the question arises, how do we as teachers make use of MI in our classrooms. Various activities that can be implemented for various learners can be as follows:

For Verbal/Linguistic learners we can use the exercises related to Reading, Vocabulary, Formal speech, Journal/diary keeping, Creative writing, Poetry, Verbal debate, extempore speaking, Humor/jokes, Storytelling etc. A Vocabulary & Grammar Learning, listening to tapes of stories, dialogues, and lectures, etc., making verbal presentation to others, making conversations, having discussions and debates, etc., creating puns, limericks, and telling jokes on topics of study, instantly speaking on a randomly drawn topic For **Body/Kinesthetic** learners Folk/creative dancing, Role playing, Physical gestures, Drama, Martial arts, Body language, Physical exercise, Mime, Invention, Sports games etc. can be included. Physical Actions like arranging and doing TPR and hands-on activities, Sports Games

On one hand Students with **Intrapersonal** skills can be taught through Silent reflection methods, Metacognitive techniques, Thinking strategies, Emotional processing "Know-thyself" procedures, Practice of mindfulness, Focusing/ concentration skills, Higher-order reasoning, Complex guided imagery and Centering practices, Independent Studies/Projects, Journals Logs/ Diaries keeping.

whereas we can make use of techniques like Giving feedback, Intuiting others' feelings, Using cooperative learning strategies, Communicating person to person, Practicing empathy, Dividing work, Developing collaboration skills, Receiving feedback, Sensing others' motives, Participating in group projects for students with **Interpersonal** skills.

For students with **Musical/Rhythmic intelligence** various Rhythmic patterns, Vocal sounds/ tones, Musical composition/creation, Percussion vibrations, Humming, Environmental sounds, Singing, Tonal patterns, Musical

performance can be implemented, or to remember certain words, sentence structures, concepts, ideas, or processes. A Vocal Sounds/Tones -- producing sounds with one's vocal cords to illustrate the meaning of a word, or a concept (e.g., hiccup, gasp, etc.)

For **Visual/Spatial** learners Guided imagery, Active imagination, Color schemes, Patterns/ designs, Painting/drawing, Mind mapping, Pretending, Sculpture, Pictures ect can be incorporated in studies. Visual Aids Using/Making and using flash cards, pictures, paintings, charts, collages, graphs, grids, diagrams, flowcharts, slides, sculptures and video/film-viewing, etc. to facilitate learning and encouraging students to make the visual aids by themselves,

Active Imagination like finding connection between visual designs (or pattern) and prior experiences (or knowledge) can be used.

For **Logical/Mathematical** learners we can use Abstract symbols and formulae, Outlining, Graphic organizers, Number sequences, Calculation, Deciphering of codes, Forcing of relationships, Problem solving and all can be used. Logic Pattern Games, logical/Sequential Presentation, number Sequences/Patterns, Problem Solving, Forming Relationships and using A Syllogisms -- making "if..., then..." logical deductions about a topic.

Naturalistic intelligence can be developed by Nature Encounters/Field Trips, Species Classification, Sensory Stimulation Exercises, Hands-On Labs, Nature World Simulations etc.

Gardner did not prepare a curriculum or a model to be used in schools with his MI theory. Educators have taken the theory, put it together in different ways, customized it according to their conditions and applied it to their lesson planning and program and curriculum development. The key points given above are all useful to the English language teaching They help us understand the diversity we observe in our students and provide a framework for addressing these differences in our teaching. Through this paper I intended to compile what Gardner proposed and all of teaching fraternity accepted. To make learning a willing process let us all identify and nurture these multiple intelligences in our students.

References

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